

PARASOCIAL IDENTITY CONTINUITY UNDER ALGORITHMIC VOICE TRANSFER

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AI voice cloning and automatic dubbing now permit well-known public figures to appear to speak languages they have never learned while preserving their recognizable voice and delivery. Previous studies have mainly evaluated technical quality and localization efficiency, while the question of how these transformations affect the continuity of celebrity persona, already shaped through parasocial relations, remains underexplored. This article approaches such cases as forms of algorithmic voice transfer in which the speaking subject is no longer singular but distributed across the human figure, the platform, and the model.

The study uses a two-stage design. First, a corpus of institutional, journalistic, and platform texts is analyzed to identify the main frames through which AI-mediated multilingual speech of public figures is presented. Topic modelling combined with automated stance detection is applied to a set of cases including humanitarian campaigns, political deepfakes, real-time multilingual interviews, and platform-level auto-dubbing. This stage shows when the mediated voice is constructed as a continuation of the public persona, as a neutral technological service, or as a replacement of the speaker.

In the second stage, the analysis is extended to platform reception through transformer-based stance detection applied to large-scale YouTube comment data. This makes it possible to examine how audiences negotiate authenticity, agency, and identity continuity when a familiar voice performs in an unfamiliar language.

The article argues that AI-mediated multilingual speech shifts the problem of authenticity from signal realism to the status of the speaking subject and offers a method for studying these negotiations in platform environments.